

Newtonized Orthogonal Matching Pursuit for High-Resolution Target Detection in Sparse OFDM ISAC Systems

Syed Najaf Haider Shah, Sebastian Semper, Aamir Ullah Khan, Christian Schneider, and Joerg Robert

This work has been submitted to the IEEE for possible publication. Copyright may be transferred without notice, after which this version may no longer be accessible.

Abstract—Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) is a technology paradigm that combines sensing capabilities with communication functionalities in a single device or system. In vehicle-to-everything (V2X) sidelink, ISAC can provide enhanced safety by allowing vehicles to not only communicate with one another but also sense the surrounding environment by using sidelink signals. In ISAC-capable V2X sidelink, the random resource allocation results in an unstructured and sparse distribution of time and frequency resources in the received orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) grid, leading to degraded radar detection performance when processed using the conventional 2D-FFT method. To address this challenge, this paper proposes a high-resolution off-grid radar target detection algorithm irrespective of the OFDM grid structure. The proposed method utilizes the Newtonized orthogonal matching pursuit (NOMP) algorithm to effectively detect weak targets masked by the sidelobes of stronger ones and accurately estimates off-grid range and velocity parameters with minimal resources through Newton refinements. Simulation results demonstrate the superior performance of the proposed NOMP-based target detection algorithm compared to existing compressed sensing (CS) methods in terms of detection probability, resolution, and accuracy. Additionally, experimental validation is performed using a bistatic radar setup in a semi-anechoic chamber. The measurement results validate the simulation findings, showing that the proposed algorithm significantly enhances target detection and parameter estimation accuracy in realistic scenarios.

Index Terms—Sparse OFDM, ISAC, Newtonized orthogonal matching pursuit, Resource Allocation, Off-grid estimation

I. INTRODUCTION

IN recent decades, the fields of wireless communications and radar sensing have witnessed significant advancements, driven by the growing demand for high-speed data transfer and precise environmental awareness. However, the rapid increase in connected devices and applications, such as autonomous driving, smart cities, and extended reality, has put immense pressure on the already crowded electromagnetic spectrum. This spectrum scarcity has led to the emergence of Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC) as a promising solution that merges communication and radar sensing functionalities within a single system. ISAC enables the efficient sharing of limited spectrum and hardware resources between these two domains, resulting in substantial cost savings and improved system performance [1], [2].

ISAC is not just about spectrum efficiency, it is also a key enabler for next-generation cellular technologies like beyond

fifth-generation (5G) and sixth-generation (6G). ISAC represents a promising key technology for enhancing connectivity and intelligent decision-making in various applications such as high-resolution sensing and tracking, simultaneous localization, mapping, and imaging [3] etc. In cellular-vehicle-to-everything (C-V2X), particularly in 6G-V2X systems, ISAC will enable vehicles to communicate with one another while simultaneously sensing their environment. This dual capability is crucial for facilitating cooperative driving, where vehicles can share information about their surroundings, road conditions, and potential hazards in real-time [4]. By integrating sensing and communication functions, ISAC enhances situational awareness, enabling vehicles to make informed decisions that improve overall traffic safety ultimately contributing to safer, more efficient, and intelligent transportation systems.

In a multiuser ISAC-capable vehicle-to-everything (V2X) sidelink system, vehicles in autonomous mode randomly select distinct frequency (subcarriers) and time (symbols) resources from an orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) resource grid to perform communication and radar sensing simultaneously [5]. This random resource selection is susceptible to mutual interference and resource collisions due to the hidden-node problem [6]. When the interfered or overlapped resources are removed from this unstructured OFDM resource grid, the received OFDM signal at the radar receiver becomes sparse in both time and frequency domain. This sparsity poses significant challenges for conventional radar processing methods, such as two dimensional fast Fourier transform (2D-FFT), multiple signal classification (MUSIC), or estimation of signal parameters via rational invariance techniques (ESPRIT), which are typically designed for either continuous or regularly spaced time-frequency OFDM signals [7]. Applying these algorithms to sparse and unstructured OFDM signals results in degraded target detection performance, where unpredictable range-Doppler sidelobes appear in the radar map. These sidelobes obscure weaker targets, making target detection difficult and unreliable [8].

To address the challenges posed by the sparse nature of the OFDM signal in ISAC systems, compressed sensing (CS) techniques offer a promising alternative. CS has been extensively utilized in both communication and radar sensing applications. In communication systems, CS is employed for channel estimation through sparse signal recovery [9], [10], while in radar sensing, it provides super-resolution and

enhanced accuracy in parameter estimation [11], [12]. Notably, CS methods have demonstrated superiority over subspace-based approaches like MUSIC in noisy environments, particularly when strong dominant clutter or direct signals are present [13]. Additionally, CS is well-suited for scenarios where continuous target observation is not feasible, as it can reconstruct signals from a small number of samples by exploiting signal sparsity, even when the sampling interval is irregular. However, CS methods are not without challenges, particularly the grid mismatch problem. This issue arises when the true parameters of a target (e.g., range and Doppler shift) do not align with the discretized grid used for parameter estimation [14]. Even with a finely discretized parameter grid, the true target parameters often fall between grid points, leading to estimation errors [15]. Furthermore, increasing the grid resolution to mitigate this issue results in a quadratic increase in computational complexity, making real-time processing impractical.

Addressing these challenges is essential to unlocking the full potential of ISAC in V2X systems and other advanced applications. Effective radar target detection in dynamic environments requires low-complexity algorithms that offer super-resolution capabilities, eliminate grid mismatches, and accurately estimate both on-grid and off-grid parameters. The development of such algorithms will be key to enabling reliable, high-precision sensing in ISAC-capable V2X systems, paving the way for safer, smarter, and more connected transportation environments.

A. Related Work

Several approaches have been proposed to address the challenges posed by sparse OFDM signals in ISAC systems. The authors in [16], [17] introduced a CS method named sparse iterative multidimensional frequency estimation (SIMFE) based on the orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP) algorithm to deal with the increased range sidelobes caused by non-equidistant subcarrier interleaving in the OFDM grid. This method exploits the idea of interpolation for an off-grid frequency estimation. However, this method focuses solely on range sidelobe suppression and does not account for sparsity in the time domain. Other approaches, such as those in [18], [19], combine the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) and Basis Pursuit (BP) algorithms to resolve ambiguities in range estimation due to random subcarrier allocation but suffer from high computational complexity. To enhance range and velocity profile reconstruction with sparse OFDM signals, approximate message passing (AMP) and split augmented Lagrangian shrinkage (SALSA) algorithms were employed in [20], [21]. However, these algorithms struggle when sparsity across OFDM symbols is considered. Moreover, these methods do not address the grid mismatch problem, which arises when true parameter values do not align with the discretized grid. To account for this issue, gridless CS methods based on atomic norm minimization (ANM) are employed to estimate off-grid parameters accurately [22], [23], but their computational complexity is often prohibitive for practical implementation.

While existing CS algorithms for sparse OFDM signals have made important strides, they exhibit several key shortcomings. Some suffer from high Doppler sidelobes due to the sparsity

along the time domain not being considered. Others fail to address the grid mismatch problem. Additionally, those that offer solutions to grid mismatch issues suffer from high computational complexity, limiting their practical use in real-time applications.

B. Contributions

To address these shortcomings, this paper proposes a super-resolution off-grid radar target detection algorithm based on the Newtonized orthogonal matching pursuit (NOMP) regardless of the OFDM grid structure. The proposed algorithm effectively detects weak targets masked by the sidelobes of strong targets in the sparse OFDM-based multiuser ISAC-capable V2X sidelink system with minimal sensing resources.

The key contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- 1) We introduce a high-resolution radar target detection algorithm that operates without restrictions on the structure of the OFDM grid, leveraging the NOMP method for both on-grid and off-grid parameter estimation. The algorithm consists of three key steps: (1) coarse on-grid estimation, (2) local Newton refinements, and (3) joint Newton refinements. In the first step, standard OMP is employed to estimate the on-grid delay and Doppler shift parameters. To accelerate the process, the conventional correlation step in the OMP is replaced with a computationally efficient 2D-FFT, ensuring faster on-grid estimation. In the second step, Newton refinements are applied iteratively to the newly detected on-grid parameter estimation, allowing for accurate off-grid parameter estimation. In the third step, joint Newton refinements are applied to all detected parameters to obtain further fine-tuned estimates. This feedback mechanism enables the re-evaluation of previously estimated parameters based on newly detected ones, improving estimation accuracy and handling target interference. To reduce the computational burden associated with joint Newton refinements, the block Hessian matrix is simplified into a block diagonal matrix, yielding a low-complexity solution. These enhancements make the proposed algorithm not only highly accurate but also computationally efficient, rendering it suitable for real-time radar target detection in multiuser ISAC systems. Moreover, the proposed algorithm does not require a priori knowledge of the number of targets for termination rather it supports a CFAR-based stopping criterion as given in [24].
- 2) The proposed algorithm is rigorously evaluated through simulations to assess its performance across several key metrics, including effective weak target recovery, detection of closely-spaced off-grid targets, root-mean-squared-error (RMSE) in range and velocity estimations, convergence behavior, and execution time. The results demonstrate the superiority of the proposed NOMP-based algorithm compared to conventional methods such as 2D-FFT, OMP, and SALSA, highlighting its enhanced ability to resolve targets under challenging conditions.

- 3) To evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithm in realistic conditions, we conducted experiments using a bi-static radar setup within a semi-anechoic chamber. The experiments were facilitated by the Virtual Road Simulation and Test Area (VISTA) at the Thuringian Center of Innovation in Mobility, providing a controlled environment for precise evaluation [25]. The measurement results corroborate the simulation findings, demonstrating the practical feasibility of the NOMP-based algorithm in real-world scenarios.

C. Notation

Scalars, vectors, matrices, and sets are denoted using different typographical conventions. Scalars are represented by italic letters (a) or Greek letters (α). Vectors are indicated by bold lowercase letters (\mathbf{a}), and matrices are denoted by bold uppercase letters (\mathbf{A}). Matrix operations follow standard mathematical conventions. \mathbf{A}^T , \mathbf{A}^H , \mathbf{A}^{-1} , \mathbf{A}^\dagger , and \mathbf{A}^* represent transpose, Hermitian transpose, inverse, pseudo-inverse, and conjugate of matrix \mathbf{A} respectively. The identity matrix of size $N \times N$ is denoted by \mathbf{I}_N . For element-wise operations, the Hadamard (element-wise) product between matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} is represented by $\mathbf{A} \circ \mathbf{B}$, and element-wise division is denoted as $\mathbf{A} \oslash \mathbf{B}$. The Kronecker product of two matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} is denoted as $\mathbf{A} \otimes \mathbf{B}$. The Fourier transform operation is denoted by $\mathcal{F}\{\cdot\}$, and its inverse by $\mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\cdot\}$. $\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$ denotes the big-O notation. Norms and other mathematical notations include the ℓ_2 norm, which is denoted as $\|\mathbf{x}\|_2$ and represents the Euclidean norm of vector \mathbf{x} .

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the ISAC system model and signal model. Section III describes the proposed high-resolution off-grid target detection algorithm using NOMP. Section IV presents the simulation results. Measurement setup and measurement results are presented in Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. ISAC-CAPABLE SIDELINK SYSTEM

We assume a scenario that consists of multiple vehicles moving on a road. The vehicles exchange data with one another through sidelink signals while also utilizing reflected sidelink signals to sense the surrounding environment, enabling a multiuser ISAC-capable sidelink. As shown in Fig. 1, in compliance with the half-duplex mode of operation in V2X sidelink communication, a transmitting vehicle (TX) transmits data packets to a receiving vehicle (RX) over the sidelink channel. The RX receives not only the direct sidelink signal from the TX but also the reflected signals from the neighbor vehicle (Strong Target) and a pedestrian (Weak Target). This configuration enables the RX to operate as a bi-static radar, utilizing the reflected sidelink signals to estimate the range and relative velocity of the targets [26]. The other vehicles (other) also communicate with the RX through the V2X sidelink multiple access technology. In this multiuser ISAC-capable sidelink setup, the TX randomly selects time and frequency resources from the OFDM resource pool which is also shared by other vehicles as shown in Fig. 2. This random selection forms

Figure 1: ISAC-capable sidelink scenario

an unstructured sparse OFDM grid which will be received by the RX for communication and radar processing. The TX also sends the information of its time-frequency resources (i.e., number and locations in the sparse OFDM grid) to the RX over the sidelink control channel so that RX have the knowledge of the TX signal.

Figure 2: The resource allocation grid obtained by random resource selection in a multiuser ISAC-capable sidelink system.

A. Signal Model

The transmitted signal $x : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ in complex baseband consists of N subcarriers and M OFDM symbols resulting in an $N \times M$ TX resource grid \mathbf{X} . Within \mathbf{X} , the TX selects a random subset Ω_s of resources from Ω where $\Omega = \{(n, m) \mid 0 < n \leq N, 0 < m \leq M\}$ and $\Omega_s \subset \Omega$. Hence, the transmit signal x is given by

$$x(t) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \left(\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \mathbf{X}_{n,m} e^{j \frac{2\pi}{T} nt} \right) \text{rect}_T(t - mT_o), \quad (1)$$

with

$$\mathbf{X}_{n,m} \in \begin{cases} \mathcal{A}_{n,m}, & \text{if } \{n, m\} \in \Omega_s \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{A}_{n,m}$, T , and T_o denote the modulation symbol (e.g., QPSK), rectangular pulse duration, and the OFDM symbol duration including the cyclic prefix (CP) respectively. The

received OFDM grid at the RX after removing the CP and taking the DFT can be written as

$$\mathbf{Y}_{n,m} = \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k \mathbf{X}_{n,m} e^{-j2\pi n \Delta f \tau_k} e^{j2\pi m T_o \alpha_k} + \mathbf{Z}_{n,m}, \quad (3)$$

where K is the total number of targets which are assumed to be placed at arbitrary locations in the parameter space, and τ_k and α_k are bi-static delay and Doppler shift of the k^{th} target at the RX respectively. The term $\beta_k = |\beta_k| e^{j\phi_k}$ is the complex attenuation coefficient which includes the attenuation constant and the phase shift of the signal reflected from the k^{th} target, and $\mathbf{Z}_{n,m}$ represents additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with zero mean.

III. OFF-GRID TARGET DETECTION USING NOMP ALGORITHM

This section introduces the proposed NOMP-based target detection algorithm that estimates the targets placed across a continuous parameter space as an off-grid sparse recovery method. First, we account for the transmitted symbols from the received OFDM signal \mathbf{Y} by element-wise division with \mathbf{X} as given in [27], [28], to obtain the frequency domain channel transfer function matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N}$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}_{n,m} &= \frac{\mathbf{Y}_{n,m}}{\mathbf{X}_{n,m}} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k e^{-j2\pi n \Delta f \tau_k} e^{j2\pi m T_o \alpha_k} + \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_{n,m}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{H} is a sparse matrix with nonzero entries located at the set of indices Ω_s . By excluding the unused resources (i.e., zero entries), the matrix \mathbf{H} is compressed to \mathbf{H}_s . We express the compressed matrix \mathbf{H}_s in vector form as

$$\mathbf{h}_s = \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k \mathbf{a}^{\Omega_s}(\tau_k, \alpha_k) + \tilde{\mathbf{z}}, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{a}^{\Omega_s}(\tau_k, \alpha_k) \in \mathbb{C}^{|\Omega_s|}$ is the response vector corresponding to the k^{th} off-grid target, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{a}^{\Omega_s}(\tau_k, \alpha_k) = [e^{-j2\pi n \Delta f \tau_k} e^{j2\pi m T_o \alpha_k}]_{\{n,m\} \in \Omega_s}. \quad (6)$$

Thus, (5) can be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{h}_s = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{b} + \tilde{\mathbf{z}}, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{a}^{\Omega_s}(\tau_1, \alpha_1), \mathbf{a}^{\Omega_s}(\tau_2, \alpha_2), \dots, \mathbf{a}^{\Omega_s}(\tau_K, \alpha_K)] \in \mathbb{C}^{|\Omega_s| \times K}$, $\mathbf{b} = [\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_K] \in \mathbb{C}^K$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{z}} \in \mathbb{C}^{|\Omega_s|}$ is the noise vector.

A. OMP

Conventional grid-based CS methods discretize the parameter plane into $N \times M$ grid points and assume that each grid point corresponds to a potential target's parameter. Let $\bar{\tau} \triangleq \{\bar{\tau}_p \in [0, \frac{d_{max}}{c}] \mid p = 1, \dots, N\}$, and $\bar{\alpha} \triangleq \{\bar{\alpha}_q \in [-\frac{2v_{max}}{\lambda}, \frac{2v_{max}}{\lambda}] \mid q = 1, \dots, M\}$, be the discretized delay and Doppler shift grids respectively, where d_{max} is the sum of the maximum transmitter-to-target range and the maximum target-to-receiver range, v_{max} is the maximum allowed relative

velocity, λ and c are the wavelength and speed of light respectively. Then, the measurement vector \mathbf{h}_s can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{h}_s = \bar{\mathbf{A}} \bar{\mathbf{b}} + \bar{\mathbf{z}}, \quad (8)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{A}} = [\mathbf{a}(\bar{\tau}_1, \bar{\alpha}_1), \mathbf{a}(\bar{\tau}_2, \bar{\alpha}_1), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\bar{\tau}_N, \bar{\alpha}_M)] \in \mathbb{C}^{|\Omega_s| \times NM}$ is the sensing matrix, $\bar{\mathbf{b}} = [\bar{\beta}_1, \bar{\beta}_2, \dots, \bar{\beta}_{NM}] \in \mathbb{C}^{NM}$ is the attenuation coefficient vector of grid points. In (8), \mathbf{h}_s and $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$ are known while $\bar{\mathbf{b}}$ is unknown. Since $|\Omega_s| \ll NM$, (8) is underdetermined, hence there is no unique solution without additional assumptions about the considered problem. When the targets are sparsely occupying the parameter space, that is, non-zero elements in the solution vector $\bar{\mathbf{b}}$ are very few, (8) can be solved by utilizing sparse recovery methods, which impose sparsity by appropriate regularization of the obtained solutions. One of the most prominent CS methods is the OMP algorithm, where the main idea is to obtain a new support element of $\bar{\mathbf{b}}$ in each iteration, by determining the maximum correlation between the residual and columns of the measurement matrix. The OMP is stated in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 The OMP Algorithm

- 1: **Input:** $\mathbf{h}_s, \bar{\mathbf{A}}, K$
 - 2: **Initial state:** $\mathbf{r}_0 = \mathbf{h}_s, \Pi_0 = \emptyset, \ell = 0$
 - 3: **repeat**
 - 4: $\ell = \ell + 1$
 - 5: **Match step:** \triangleright Compute the correlation
 - 6: $\mathbf{c}_\ell = \bar{\mathbf{A}}^H \mathbf{r}_{\ell-1}$
 - 7: **Identify step:** \triangleright Potential basis mismatch here
 - 8: $\Pi_\ell = \Pi_{\ell-1} \cup \{\arg \max_j |\mathbf{c}_\ell(j)|^2\}$
 - 9: **Update step:** \triangleright Basis mismatch affects this step
 - 10: $\bar{\mathbf{b}}_\ell = \arg \min_{\mathbf{v}: \text{supp}(\mathbf{v}) \subseteq \Pi_\ell} \|\mathbf{h}_s - \bar{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{v}\|_2^2$
 - 11: $\mathbf{r}_\ell = \mathbf{h}_s - \bar{\mathbf{A}} \bar{\mathbf{b}}_\ell$ \triangleright Update the residue
 - 12: **until** $\ell = K$
 - 13: **Output:** $\bar{\mathbf{b}}_K, \Pi_K$
-

However, the OMP suffers from the basis mismatch issue; that is, when the target lies off the grid points constituting $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{b}}$, its performance degrades. In Algorithm 1, the *identify step* selects the atom with the highest correlation to the current residual. However, when the target lies between two grid points, the selected atom will not perfectly align with the actual target, leading to a mismatch that is later accounted for by the estimation of spurious ghost paths, i.e., the algorithm proposes detected target locations that have no physical justification. This mismatch also further propagates to the *update step*, where the residual is updated based on a suboptimal atom selection, thereby reducing the accuracy of the reconstructed signal and also the reliability of the estimated target parameters.

B. NOMP

To address this limitation, we introduce a high-resolution off-grid target detection method using the NOMP algorithm. The NOMP extends the OMP by introducing Newton refinements to mitigate the basis mismatch. The proposed algorithm roughly involves three steps: 1) making a coarse estimation of a new target's parameters on a discrete grid using the OMP, 2)

performing local optimization using Newton refinements in the vicinity of the coarse estimate, essentially introducing off-grid estimates, 3) conducting global optimization using Newton refinements for all previously identified targets jointly. By introducing these steps, the algorithm mitigates the impact of basis mismatch, resulting in improved performance compared to standard OMP, especially when the target lies off the discretized grid points.

Let $\mathcal{C} = \{\tau_\ell, \alpha_\ell, \beta_\ell \mid \ell = 1, \dots, K\}$ represent the set of parameters to be estimated. The corresponding residual will be calculated by

$$\mathbf{h}_r(\mathcal{C}) = \mathbf{h}_s - \sum_{\ell=1}^K \beta_\ell \mathbf{a}^{\Omega_s}(\tau_\ell, \alpha_\ell). \quad (9)$$

We obtain the maximum likelihood estimate of \mathcal{C} by minimizing the residual energy $\|\mathbf{h}_r(\mathcal{C})\|_2^2$. However, it is computationally inefficient to directly minimize the residual w.r.t all parameters. Therefore, we estimate the parameters of multiple targets by performing Newtonian gradient descent for each target's parameters individually using the coarse estimation result of OMP as on-grid initial estimates.

1) *Initial Coarse Estimation*: We first perform a coarse detection of τ_ℓ and α_ℓ within respective discrete grids $\bar{\tau}$ and $\bar{\alpha}$. The coarse estimate of (τ_ℓ, α_ℓ) is obtained by the OMP method summarized in Algorithm 1, where the *match step* involves computing the correlations between the residual and the columns of the sensing matrix $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$. However, when $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$ is a large matrix, this step incurs a high computational cost due to the large number of matrix-vector multiplications. To reduce the computational complexity, we propose a modification by exploiting the structure of the sensing matrix. We know that in our sensing scenario the sensing matrix $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$ can be written as:

$$\bar{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{I}_s(\mathbf{F}_m^* \otimes \mathbf{F}_n), \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{I}_s \in \mathbb{C}^{|\Omega_s| \times NM}$ is a selection matrix, and $\mathbf{F}_n \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ and $\mathbf{F}_m \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ are Fourier matrices. This decomposition allows us to take advantage of the fast Fourier transform (FFT) for faster computation. To this end, we define a matrix $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$, whose entries at the indices Ω_s are initialized with the values of the residual vector \mathbf{h}_r , (i.e., $\mathbf{R}(\Omega_s) = \mathbf{h}_r$). Then, we exploit the FFT to compute the correlation as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{c}_\ell &= (\mathbf{I}_s(\mathbf{F}_m^* \otimes \mathbf{F}_n))^H \mathbf{h}_r \\ &= \text{vec}(\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\mathbf{R}))^T) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Here, \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{F}^{-1} represent the FFT and IFFT, respectively, and $\text{vec}(\cdot)$ vectorizes the resulting matrix. By using (IFFT) we significantly reduce the computational complexity of the correlation step from $\mathcal{O}(|\Omega_s|NM)$ (i.e., direct matrix multiplication) to $\mathcal{O}(NM(\log(N) + \log(M)))$.

Once the correlation vector \mathbf{c}_ℓ is computed, the coarse on-grid estimate $(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)$ is selected as

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_\ell &= \arg \max_j |\mathbf{c}_\ell(j)|^2, \\ (\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell) &= \text{ind2sub}([N, M], \Pi_\ell), \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where the function `ind2sub` converts linear index Π_ℓ to subscript indices $\hat{\tau}_\ell$ and $\hat{\alpha}_\ell$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\tau}_\ell &= \Pi_\ell - (\lceil \Pi_\ell / N \rceil - 1)N, \\ \hat{\alpha}_\ell &= \lceil \Pi_\ell / N \rceil. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

We obtain the corresponding attenuation coefficients $\hat{\beta}_\ell$ by invoking step 10 of Algorithm 1. Hereafter in all subsequent sections, we assume $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}^{\Omega_s}$ for clarity and brevity.

2) *Local Newton Refinements*: In this step, the coarse estimates $(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell, \hat{\beta}_\ell)$ of a newly detected target are refined by the Newton method. The refined estimates of the coarse estimates are obtained by solving the non-linear least squares problem $\|\mathbf{h}_r - \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)\hat{\beta}_\ell\|_2^2$, which is equivalent to maximizing

$$\mathbf{S}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell, \hat{\beta}_\ell) = 2\Re\left\{\mathbf{h}_r^H \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)\hat{\beta}_\ell\right\} - |\hat{\beta}_\ell|^2 \|\mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)\|_2^2. \quad (14)$$

The Newton refinement of $(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)$ is done by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\tau}'_\ell \\ \hat{\alpha}'_\ell \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\tau}_\ell \\ \hat{\alpha}_\ell \end{bmatrix} - \check{\mathbf{S}}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell, \hat{\beta}_\ell)^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{S}}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell, \hat{\beta}_\ell), \quad (15)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{S}}$ is known as the Jacobian matrix and is defined as

$$\dot{\mathbf{S}}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell, \hat{\beta}_\ell) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}}{\partial \hat{\tau}_\ell} \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}}{\partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

and $\check{\mathbf{S}}$ is known as the Hessian matrix and is defined as

$$\check{\mathbf{S}}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell, \hat{\beta}_\ell) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}}{\partial \hat{\tau}_\ell^2} & \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}}{\partial \hat{\tau}_\ell \partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell} \\ \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}}{\partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell \partial \hat{\tau}_\ell} & \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}}{\partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell^2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

The first order partial derivatives of \mathbf{S} w.r.t $\hat{\tau}_\ell$ and $\hat{\alpha}_\ell$ are computed as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{S}}{\partial \hat{\tau}_\ell} = 2\Re\left\{\left(\mathbf{h}_r - \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)\hat{\beta}_\ell\right)^H \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\tau}_\ell} \hat{\beta}_\ell\right\}, \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{S}}{\partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell} = 2\Re\left\{\left(\mathbf{h}_r - \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)\hat{\beta}_\ell\right)^H \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell} \hat{\beta}_\ell\right\}. \quad (19)$$

Similarly, the second-order derivatives are computed as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}}{\partial \hat{\tau}_\ell^2} &= 2\Re\left\{\left(\mathbf{h}_r - \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)\hat{\beta}_\ell\right)^H \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\tau}_\ell^2} \hat{\beta}_\ell \right. \\ &\quad \left. - |\hat{\beta}_\ell|^2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\tau}_\ell} \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\tau}_\ell}\right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}}{\partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell^2} &= 2\Re\left\{\left(\mathbf{h}_r - \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)\hat{\beta}_\ell\right)^H \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell^2} \hat{\beta}_\ell \right. \\ &\quad \left. - |\hat{\beta}_\ell|^2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell} \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell}\right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}}{\partial \hat{\tau}_\ell \partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell} &= \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}}{\partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell \partial \hat{\tau}_\ell} \\ &= 2\Re\left\{\left(\mathbf{h}_r - \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)\hat{\beta}_\ell\right)^H \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell \partial \hat{\tau}_\ell} \hat{\beta}_\ell \right. \\ &\quad \left. - |\hat{\beta}_\ell|^2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}_\ell} \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\tau}_\ell}\right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

When plugging these into (15) and iterating it, we obtain the locally refined delay $\hat{\tau}'_\ell$ and Doppler shift $\hat{\alpha}'_\ell$ estimates. Then

we can update the target's attenuation coefficient $\hat{\beta}'_\ell$ at the end of each Newton refinement step via

$$\hat{\beta}'_\ell = \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell) \mathbf{h}_r / \|\mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)\|_2^2. \quad (23)$$

Finally, the residual vector \mathbf{h}_r will be updated according to (9). This step is repeated R_s times, where R_s is the number of Newton refinements.

3) *Global Newton Refinements*: After the Newton refinements of individual targets' parameters, the estimated refined parameters set is $\mathcal{C}' = \{(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell, \hat{\beta}'_\ell) \mid \ell = 1, \dots, K\}$. In this step, all the refined estimates $(\tau'_\ell, \alpha'_\ell, \beta'_\ell)$ in \mathcal{C}' are *jointly* fine-tuned via the joint Newton refinements. Consider K^{th} round, where K number of targets have been discovered. At this point, we jointly fine-update the targets' estimates using the following optimization problem.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{S}(\mathcal{C}') &= \|\mathbf{h}_r - \sum_{\ell=1}^K \hat{\beta}'_\ell \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)\|_2^2 \\ &= \|\mathbf{h}_r - \mathbf{A}_{\mathcal{C}'} \mathbf{b}_{\mathcal{C}'}\|_2^2. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

This problem can be solved by the joint Newton refinement method as given below.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\tau}''_1, \dots, \hat{\tau}''_K \\ \hat{\alpha}''_1, \dots, \hat{\alpha}''_K \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\tau}'_1, \dots, \hat{\tau}'_K \\ \hat{\alpha}'_1, \dots, \hat{\alpha}'_K \end{bmatrix} - \ddot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}')^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}'), \quad (25)$$

where, $\ddot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}') \in \mathbb{R}^{2K \times 2K}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}') \in \mathbb{R}^{2K \times 1}$ are block Hessian and block Jacobian matrices, which are given below.

$$\ddot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}') = \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{11} & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{12} & \cdots & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{1K} \\ \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{21} & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{22} & \cdots & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{2K} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{K1} & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{K2} & \cdots & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{KK} \end{bmatrix}, \dot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}') = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{S}}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \dot{\mathbf{S}}_K \end{bmatrix}. \quad (26)$$

The expressions of the entries of the matrix $\ddot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}')$, and the matrix $\dot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}')$ are rather lengthy and can be found in the Appendix.

Notably, due to the block hessian matrix structure, the computational complexity of the joint Newton refinement step in (25) is $\mathcal{O}((3K)^3)$ which increases non-linearly with the number of targets. Thus, we propose low-complexity update by relaxing the block Hessian matrix to a block diagonal matrix as

$$\ddot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}') = \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{11} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{22} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{KK} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (27)$$

This reduces the complexity to $\mathcal{O}(K)$ per step. Finally the attenuation coefficients vector $\mathbf{b}_{\mathcal{C}''}$ corresponding to the updated parameters set $\mathcal{C}'' = \{(\hat{\tau}''_\ell, \hat{\alpha}''_\ell, \hat{\beta}''_\ell) \mid \ell = 1, \dots, K\}$ is obtained by least squares method as

$$\mathbf{b}_{\mathcal{C}''} = \mathbf{A}_{\mathcal{C}''}^\dagger \mathbf{h}_s, \quad (28)$$

where, $\mathbf{A}_{\mathcal{C}''} \triangleq [\mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}''_1, \hat{\alpha}''_1), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}''_K, \hat{\alpha}''_K)]$.

The algorithm terminates when $\max_j |\mathbf{c}_\ell(j)|^2 \leq \delta$, where $\delta \triangleq \ln |\Omega_s| - \ln(-\ln(1 - p_{fa}))$ is a CFAR-based threshold,

which is selected based on the required probability of false alarm p_{fa} [24].

The proposed NOMP-based algorithm is stated in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 Proposed NOMP-based Algorithm

```

1: Input:  $\mathbf{h}_s, \bar{\mathbf{A}}, \delta$ 
2: Initial state:  $\mathbf{h}_r = \mathbf{h}_s, \Pi_0 = \emptyset, \ell = 0, \mathbf{R}^0(\Omega_s) = \mathbf{h}_r$ 
3: repeat
4:    $\ell = \ell + 1$ 
5:   Initial Coarse Estimation:
6:      $\mathbf{c}_\ell = \text{vec}(\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\mathbf{R}^{\ell-1}))^T) \triangleright$  Faster computation
7:      $\Pi_\ell = \arg \max_j |\mathbf{c}_\ell(j)|^2$ 
8:      $(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell) = \text{ind2sub}(\text{size}(\mathbf{R}), \Pi_\ell)$ 
9:      $\hat{\beta}_\ell = \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell) \mathbf{h}_r / \|\mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell)\|_2^2$ 
10:  Local Newton Refinement:  $\triangleright$  Iterate  $R_s$  times
11:     $(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell) = (\hat{\tau}_\ell, \hat{\alpha}_\ell) - \ddot{\mathbf{S}}^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{S}}$ 
12:     $\hat{\beta}'_\ell = \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell) \mathbf{h}_r / \|\mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)\|_2^2$ 
13:     $\mathbf{h}_r = \mathbf{h}_s - \hat{\beta}'_\ell \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)$ 
14:     $\mathcal{C}' = \mathcal{C}' \cup (\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell, \hat{\beta}'_\ell) \triangleright$  Local refined estimates
15:  Global Newton Refinement:
16:     $(\hat{\tau}''_\ell, \hat{\alpha}''_\ell) = (\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell) - \ddot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}')^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{S}}(\mathcal{C}') \triangleright 1 \leq \ell \leq K$ 
17:     $\mathbf{b}_{\mathcal{C}''} = \mathbf{A}_{\mathcal{C}''}^\dagger \mathbf{h}_s \triangleright$  Least squares gain update
18:     $\mathbf{h}_r = \mathbf{h}_s - \mathbf{A}_{\mathcal{C}''} \mathbf{b}_{\mathcal{C}''} \triangleright$  Update the residue
19:     $\mathbf{R}^\ell(\Omega_s) = \mathbf{h}_r \triangleright$  Update the  $\mathbf{R}$  matrix
20:     $\Pi_\ell = \Pi_{\ell-1} \cup \text{sub2ind}(\text{size}(\mathbf{R}), \hat{\tau}''_\ell, \hat{\alpha}''_\ell)$ 
21:  until  $\max |\mathbf{c}_\ell|^2 \leq \delta$ 
22: Output:  $\mathbf{b}_{\mathcal{C}''}, \Pi$ 

```

C. Computational Complexity Analysis

In this subsection, we analyze the computational complexity of the proposed NOMP-based algorithm. The Algorithm 2 has three major parts: Initial coarse estimation (steps 6-9), Local Newton refinement (steps 11-14), and Global Newton refinement (steps 16-20), and the computational complexity of each part is $\mathcal{O}(NM(\log(N) + \log(M)))$, $\mathcal{O}(kR_s|\Omega_s|)$, and $\mathcal{O}(|\Omega_s|k^2 + k^3)$, respectively, where k represents the current number of iterations.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithm and compare it with conventional 2D-FFT, SALSA [20], and OMP algorithm. We simulate an ISAC scenario consisting of a TX vehicle, RX vehicle, and a variable number of targets (i.e., vehicles and pedestrians) moving on a road. The TX and RX vehicles are equipped with single TX and single RX omnidirectional antennas respectively, for half-duplex communication and bi-static radar sensing. The sparse OFDM grid parameters used by the TX and RX vehicles, and other simulation parameters are shown in Table I.

To show the ability of the proposed method to detect weak targets (e.g., pedestrians) in the presence of strong targets (e.g., vehicles) and AWGN, we evaluate the probability of detection as a function of strong-to-weak-target peak ratio (SWPR) as shown in Fig. 3. The larger values of SWPR

Table I: Simulation Parameters

Symbol	Parameter	Value
f_c	Carrier frequency	5.90 GHz
N	Total subcarriers	1560
$n \in \Omega_s$	Subcarriers used per OFDM symbol	78
M	Total OFDM symbols	280
$m \in \Omega_s$	OFDM symbols used in OFDM grid	56
η	Resource occupancy	1.0 %
B	Bandwidth	46.8 MHz
Δf	Subcarrier spacing	30.0 kHz
K	Number of targets	variable
R_s	Newton refinement steps	5

implies lower peak power of weak targets. The 2D-FFT shows worst performance followed by SALSA and OMP. The SALSA and OMP fully recovers weak targets up to SWPR of about 6.0 dB and 14.0 dB respectively. The NOMP-based algorithm outperforms all approaches with perfect recovery of weak targets upto SWPR of about 23.0 dB.

Figure 3: Probability of weak target detection in the presence of strong target

Next, we evaluate the ability to distinguish two closely spaced off-grid targets in both the range and velocity domain as shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 respectively. In the range domain, the two targets are separated by 0.50 m (i.e., one is kept at 100 m while the other is placed at 100.5 m) as shown in the maximized region of Fig. 4. The 2D-FFT and SALSA show similar performance and can recover only one target with a peak at the grid point close to the true range. The OMP detects both targets but with inadequate accuracy (i.e., the peak of the second target is more than 2.0 m away from the true range). The NOMP not only successfully distinguishes two close targets but also accurately estimates the off-grid ranges. On the other hand, in the velocity domain, the two targets are separated by 1.0 m s^{-1} (i.e., one is moving at 23.0 m s^{-1} while the other is at 24.0 m s^{-1}) as shown in Fig. 5. Here, the 2D-FFT and SALSA show the worst performance with sidelobes comparable in magnitude to the main lobe (e.g. peak-to-sidelobe ratio (PSLR) of around 1.50 dB is observed). This behavior can lead to false target detections and reduced overall detection reliability and accuracy. Moreover, both algorithms fail to resolve the targets in the velocity domain and produce

Figure 4: Recovery of two closely spaced off-grid targets in range domain

a single merged main lobe appearing at the nearest grid point to one of the true target velocities. The OMP again shows two peaks, one is quite accurate while the other has a deviation of around 2.0 m s^{-1} . The NOMP outperforms the OMP by estimating the off-grid velocities with minimum deviations.

Figure 5: Recovery of two closely spaced off-grid targets in velocity domain

Then we investigate the estimation accuracies of the aforementioned algorithms as a function of SNR. We evaluate the RMSE in the range and velocity estimation for a single target case ($K = 1$) by running 500 independent Monte Carlo (MC) simulations for each SNR. In each MC iteration, the subset Ω_s of resources is randomly selected to form sparse TX matrix \mathbf{X} , and the noise matrix \mathbf{Z} is also randomly generated, following Gaussian distribution. The target's range and velocity are randomly chosen from $\mathcal{U}(50.0 \text{ m}, 1500 \text{ m})$ and $\mathcal{U}(-30.0 \text{ m s}^{-1}, 30.0 \text{ m s}^{-1})$ respectively. The Cramer-Rao bound (CRB) given in [29] is taken as a benchmark. The CRBs

for range and velocity estimation are expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{range}^2 &\geq \frac{3c^2}{\text{SNR}8\pi^2 MN(n^2 - 1)\Delta f^2}, \\ \sigma_{velocity}^2 &\geq \frac{3c^2}{\text{SNR}8\pi^2 f_c^2 MN(m^2 - 1)T_o^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

The RMSEs in range and velocity estimation are shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 respectively, which show that the proposed NOMP-based algorithm not only outperforms the other three approaches but also gradually approaches the CRB. When increasing the Newton refinements from $R_s = 5$ to $R_s = 10$, the RMSE range and velocity curves converge faster and meet the CRB curve. Thus a trade-off exists between accuracy requirements and complexity. On the other hand, since the 2D-FFT, SALSA, and OMP support on-grid target search, their RMSEs (i.e., in both range and velocity estimation) no longer improve with the increase in SNR.

Figure 6: RMSE in range estimation

Figure 7: RMSE in velocity estimation

In Fig. 8, we illustrate the convergence rate of the NOMP and compare it with that of the OMP. We analyze the effect of the oversampling factor (γ) on the convergence rate. By setting $\gamma = 4$. and $K = 6$, we simulate the norm of the residual as a function of the number of iterations. The results

show that the NOMP, both with and without oversampling, converges much faster than the OMP in both cases. In fact, the NOMP reduces the residual energy more quickly by utilizing the local and joint Newton refinements steps. The NOMP with oversampling converges after 6 iterations (equal to K) while NOMP without oversampling achieves convergence after 7 iterations estimating one spurious ghost target. The convergence times for the NOMP with and without oversampling are 3.95s and 1.03s, respectively. In contrast, the OMP takes 195s with the oversampling factor and 56.2s without it. These simulations were conducted on a 3.00 GHz Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-7400 CPU.

Figure 8: Convergence rates of OMP and NOMP with and without over-sampled grid at $K = 6$

In Fig. 9, we show the execution time per iteration of the OMP, NOMP, and their faster implementations. Both OMP and NOMP compute the correlations between the residual and the columns of the sensing matrix in each iteration, which has a computational complexity of $\mathcal{O}(\gamma|\Omega_s|(MN))$. By replacing this correlation step with a more efficient 2D-FFT operation, the complexity of the algorithms can be reduced to $\mathcal{O}(\gamma|\Omega_s|\log(MN))$, leading to faster implementations.

V. MEASUREMENT SETUP

To validate the proposed algorithm, we employ a bi-static radar setup in a semi-anechoic chamber, namely the Virtual Road Simulation and Test Area (VISTA), at the Thuringian Center of Innovation in Mobility. VISTA features a metal-shielded semi-anechoic chamber with inner dimensions of 13.0m \times 9.0m \times 7.5m. This chamber is equipped with a 6.50m diameter turntable and an 8.0m diameter spherical near-field antenna measurement system. This state-of-the-art test facility supports various RF measurement setups, including automotive antenna measurements, over-the-air channel emulation, and automotive radar testing [30]. To conduct bi-static dynamic scattering measurements for predefined traffic reference scenarios under reproducible laboratory conditions, it is essential to cover the full range of bi-static angles from 0° to 360° , as well as the complete spectrum of bi-static Doppler frequencies, which vary based on the target velocity [31].

Figure 9: Execution time per iteration comparison of OMP, NOMP, and their faster implementations as a function of number of targets

A. Bi-static Radar Configuration

Fig. 10 depicts the bi-static setup, with the transmitter placed outside the turntable and the receiver mounted on it. By positioning the radar target at the rotational center of the turntable, this configuration allows the bi-static angle to be varied across the full 360° azimuth range. In the context of

Figure 10: Bi-static radar configuration with metallic spheres emulating rotating targets

stationary radar networks, the Doppler effect observed during measurements is a result of the motion of radar targets. To effectively validate the estimation outcomes, it is essential that this movement can be described analytically, thereby providing the necessary ground truth data. This approach ensures that the measurement setup adequately simulates real-world conditions and allows for precise evaluation of the radar system's performance.

B. Target Emulator and Measurement Hardware

The objective of the target emulator is to replicate Doppler frequencies typical of urban traffic scenarios within a straightforward and reproducible test setup. This approach allows the signal processing software and its algorithms to be tested and

evaluated under well-controlled laboratory conditions before moving to more resource-intensive field tests. Fig. 11 illustrates the measurement setup, which includes the carousel-type bi-static Doppler target emulator. The VISTA facility features

Figure 11: Photograph of the bi-static test setup at VISTA [25]. The metallic spheres on the target emulators, and the receiver are mounted on the turntable, while the transmitter is placed outside the turntable. Pyramidal-shaped cones are microwave absorbers that are used to minimize ground reflections.

a turntable used to vary the angle between the transmitter and receiver. The transmit antenna is placed outside the turntable while the receive antenna is on the turntable. A motor equipped with an absolute angle value encoder ensures constant target velocities and provides continuous knowledge of the target positions. Two wooden cantilever beams with a span of 3.0 m are attached to the motor's rotational center, with metallic spheres mounted at the ends to serve as radar targets. The Doppler target emulator generates reproducible experimental data by ensuring strict synchronization between the RF measurements and the time-varying speeds and angles of the rotating cantilever beams. Two software-defined radio devices from the National Instruments, namely Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) 2954R are utilized to feed the spatially separated transmitter and receiver. These devices facilitate precise time synchronization with 10.0 MHz and 1 pulse per second signals shared between the transmitter and receiver. USRPs lack internal data storage capabilities and instead stream the measured data samples to and from a server connected via Ethernet. Since the sampling clocks are derived from the 10.0 MHz signal, all samples on the Rx and Tx are inherently time-stamped. In addition to data streaming, the Rx server controls the VISTA turntable and the motor of the radar target emulator.

C. Measurement Parameters

To maximize the spatial resolution of radar-based range measurements, the USRPs are configured to operate at their maximum analog frequency bandwidth of 160 MHz, centered at 5.90 GHz. The radar signals used in the measurements are typical OFDM symbols of LTE. The wideband transmit signal, a Newman sequence, is continuously transmitted with a period of $64.0 \mu\text{s}$ similar to LTE symbol duration (i.e. $66.7 \mu\text{s}$).

We conduct measurements of 4 different setups. Each setup has a specific combination of sphere diameter and angular speed as shown in Table II. Setups 1 and 2 involve small-sized

Table II: Radar Target Parameters

Setup	Sphere diameter	Angular speed
Setup 1	6.0 cm	60.0 rpm
Setup 2	6.0 cm	80.0 rpm
Setup 3	12.0 cm	30.0 rpm
Setup 4	12.0 cm	60.0 rpm

spheres (6.0 cm diameter) rotating at two different speeds: 60.0 rpm (slow) and 80.0 rpm (fast) respectively. On the other hand, setups 3 and 4 feature large-sized spheres (12.0 cm diameter) rotating at speeds of 30.0 rpm (slow) and 60.0 rpm (fast) respectively. The maximum rotation speed of 80.0 rpm ensures tangential velocities of the spheres up to 45.0 km h^{-1} , which is comparable to realistic vehicle speed in urban traffic. To emulate various combinations of bi-static delay and Doppler shift, we measure a full rotation of the turntable in 5.0° increments for each setup. During the data recording, the turntable remains stationary while the motor operates at a constant speed. This allows comprehensive evaluations of the NOMP algorithm under controlled and reproducible conditions.

D. Data Processing and Parameter Estimation

The data processing and parameter estimation start with the time-variant frequency response of the channel matrix \mathbf{H} , obtained through the element-wise division between the measured received frequency spectrum \mathbf{Y} and the predefined transmit frequency spectrum \mathbf{X} . We select a coherent block of the first 200 symbols from \mathbf{H} , which we refer to as the \mathbf{H}_c matrix. This block of 200 symbols results in an observation time of 12.8 ms, providing a Doppler resolution of 78.125 Hz. Given the frequency bandwidth of 160 MHz, a delay resolution of 6.25 ns is achieved. Next, exponential averaging-based background subtraction [32] is applied to \mathbf{H}_c to eliminate contributions from static objects, which exhibit zero Doppler shifts. This step ensures that only the dynamic components, indicative of moving spheres, remain in the processed data. Subsequently, we construct an unstructured sparse matrix by randomly selecting a subset Ω_s of time and frequency samples from the \mathbf{H}_c matrix. By excluding unused samples from the \mathbf{H}_c matrix, we compress it to a sparse matrix \mathbf{H}_s . For the parameter estimation, \mathbf{H}_s and its corresponding sensing matrix are input to the NOMP algorithm. We repeat this process for each consecutive block of 200 coherent symbols using the same set of resources Ω_s until the last block to assess the performance of the NOMP algorithm for every degree of motor rotation over a complete rotation. These processing steps ensure a detailed evaluation of the NOMP's efficacy in estimating delays and Doppler shifts in sparse OFDM ISAC systems, providing validation of the proposed NOMP-based target detection method through experimental results.

E. Measurement Results

Fig. 12 presents a comparison of delay and Doppler shift estimation results using the proposed NOMP-based algorithm

across all four setups, along with the analytically calculated delay and Doppler shift (i.e., ground truths) for one complete rotation of the target emulator. The NOMP utilizes $|\Omega_s| = 1.0\%$ of the total time and frequency samples in \mathbf{H}_c for the delay and Doppler shift estimations in all four setups. Since the measurements are conducted in a semi-anechoic chamber, reflections from the test environment are reduced. Additionally, reflections from static objects (e.g., motor and antenna arch in VISTA, etc.) are minimized by using the background subtraction algorithm, ensuring that only reflections from the two moving spheres are processed. Consequently, the sparsity level in the NOMP is set to 2 in the estimation results shown. Across the four setups, the NOMP successfully estimates the delay and Doppler shift of the moving spheres with high accuracy, even when using only $\eta = 1.0\%$ resources. This efficiency is evident in the close alignment of the estimations with the ground truths, underscoring the algorithm's performance in different scenarios involving different target sizes and angular speeds. The missing estimation points in all setups highlight a critical observation regarding the use of directional horn antennas in the measurement setup. As the spheres rotate, they periodically leave the antennas' field of view, causing the reflected signal power to drop below detectable levels. This effect is more pronounced in setups with higher angular speeds, especially in setup 2, where the spheres move at 80.0 rpm through the antenna's field of view, reducing the likelihood of continuous detection.

In addition to the results obtained using the NOMP algorithm, delay and Doppler shift estimations are also performed using the OMP algorithm, with an oversampled grid ($\gamma = 4$), for setups 2 and 4 as shown in Fig. 13. Both setups are evaluated under the same conditions as in the NOMP case to enable a direct comparison between the two algorithms. The results illustrate that the OMP algorithm, while capable of performing estimations, suffers from the inherent limitation of on-grid estimations. Due to the discretization of the parameter space, OMP relies on a fixed grid, and as a result, its estimations tend to snap to the closest grid point, leading to inaccurate target detection. This is due to the basis mismatch problem not handled by the OMP algorithm. In contrast, the NOMP overcomes this problem by introducing Newton refinements steps resulting in superior detection accuracy as evident from the much closer alignment between the NOMP estimations and the ground truths. This comparison underscores the limitations of traditional grid-based approaches like OMP in applications where high precision is required, especially in high mobility ISAC scenarios.

To evaluate the accuracy of the estimation results, the error distributions of the estimated delay and Doppler shift across the four setups are plotted using box plots as shown in Fig. 14. To further analyze the impact of resource utilization on estimation accuracy, 50 simulations are performed for each setup using $\eta = 1.0\%$, $\eta = 5.0\%$, and $\eta = 10.0\%$ of the total time-frequency resources. For each simulation, the percentage of resources is randomly selected from the \mathbf{H}_c matrix, ensuring a variety of time-frequency combinations are tested. Fig. 14a presents the box plot of absolute delay errors, while Fig. 14b shows the absolute Doppler shift errors.

Figure 12: Comparison of delay and Doppler shift estimations in (a) Setup 1, (b) Setup 2, (c) Setup 3, and (d) Setup 4 with the ground truths for one complete rotation of the target emulator. The color of the estimations represents the magnitude of the moving spheres throughout the complete rotation.

Figure 13: Delay and Doppler shift estimations results in (a) Setup 2 and (b) Setup 4, using OMP with oversampled grid ($\gamma = 4$). The color of the estimations represents the magnitude of the moving spheres throughout the complete rotation.

The results indicate that the error in delay estimation is generally lower in setups 3 and 4, which involve spheres with a larger diameter (12.0 cm), compared to setups 1 and 2, which feature spheres with a smaller diameter (6.0 cm). This suggests that larger spheres having larger radar cross-section (RCS) provide more accurate delay estimations. A larger RCS leads to stronger reflected signals, increasing the SNR at the receiver. Higher SNR improves the ability of the NOMP to distinguish between the signal and noise, leading to a more accurate estimation of delay. In contrast, smaller spheres with lower RCS produce weaker reflections, resulting in lower SNR, and hence, more estimation errors. Additionally, across all four setups, the delay estimation error consistently decreases as resource utilization increases, demonstrating that greater resource allocation enhances estimation accuracy. In terms of Doppler shift estimation, the error is most prominent in setup 2, where the spheres rotate at 80.0 rpm. The higher angular speed in this setup introduces more variability in the Doppler shift, leading to greater estimation errors compared to the other setups. A similar trend is observed in Doppler shift estimation errors with respect to resource utilization, where increasing the percentage of utilized resources reduces the error. These findings highlight the importance of adequate resource allocation in improving the accuracy of delay and Doppler shift estimation, especially under challenging conditions such as higher angular velocities or smaller target sizes.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a high-resolution off-grid target detection algorithm based on the Newtonized Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (NOMP). The proposed algorithm is suitable for a multiuser Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) system with arbitrary orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) resource grid structure. The proposed algorithm has three main stages. In the first stage, the algorithm provides an initial coarse estimate of the target's delay and Doppler shift parameters based on discretized grid points. In the second stage, this rough on-grid estimate is refined in the surrounding two-dimensional continuous delay-Doppler space using the Newton method. Finally, in the third stage, a global joint feedback optimization is applied to all estimated targets. This joint feedback optimization allows inaccurately identified targets with small spacing to be updated and potentially separated more accurately, improving the delay-Doppler resolution. The proposed algorithm offers not only effective and accurate gridless target detection thanks to Newton refinements but also high computational efficiency. Additionally, the algorithm does not require prior knowledge of the number of targets for termination, which makes it suitable for realistic scenarios. Besides, the proposed algorithm outperforms the existing typical methods in weak target recovery under strong target components, detection of closely spaced off-grid targets, estimation accuracy, convergence rate, and execution time. Furthermore, the feasibility of the algorithm is validated using bi-static radar measurement data with dynamic radar targets in a metal-shielded semi-anechoic chamber. The measurement results showed that the proposed NOMP-based algorithm can

(a) Box plots of absolute delay error distribution across 4 setups.

(b) Box plots of absolute Doppler error distribution across 4 setups.

Figure 14: (a) Setups 3 and 4, which feature larger spheres with larger RCS, exhibit lower median and overall error compared to setups 1 and 2 with smaller spheres. (b) Setup 2 with the fastest moving spheres shows the largest Doppler estimation error compared to other setups.

accurately detect targets with only 1.0% of the total OFDM resources, significantly reducing the OFDM resource occupancy for radar sensing in ISAC system.

In future work, we can employ the proposed algorithm in resource allocation strategies in ISAC systems. Given that the algorithm efficiently handles sparse and unstructured OFDM grids, it can be utilized to optimize resource allocation in multiuser ISAC-capable V2X sidelink systems. By incorporating the algorithm into advanced resource management techniques, the resource occupancy for high-resolution radar sensing can be minimized in dense ISAC systems. Additionally, extending the algorithm to account for multi-dimensional parameters beyond range and velocity, such as angle-of-arrival, can enable its application in more complex vehicular networks and urban scenarios.

APPENDIX

In (26), the block Hessian matrix $\ddot{\mathbf{S}}(C')$ and the block Jacobian matrix $\dot{\mathbf{S}}(C')$ are defined. The entry $\dot{\mathbf{S}}_\ell$ in $\dot{\mathbf{S}}(C')$ is the Jacobian matrix of the ℓ^{th} target and is defined as

$$\dot{\mathbf{S}}_\ell = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (30)$$

where the first order partial derivatives of $\mathbf{S}(C')$ w.r.t $\hat{\tau}'_\ell$ and $\hat{\alpha}'_\ell$ are computed as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} = 2\Re \left\{ (\mathbf{h}_r - \mathbf{A}_{C'} \mathbf{b}_{C'})^H \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} \hat{\beta}'_\ell \right\}, \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} = 2\Re \left\{ (\mathbf{h}_r - \mathbf{A}_{C'} \mathbf{b}_{C'})^H \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} \hat{\beta}'_\ell \right\}, \quad (32)$$

whereas the entry $\ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{\ell k}$ in $\ddot{\mathbf{S}}(C')$ is the Hessian matrix, and is defined for two cases: Case 1 when $\ell = k$ and Case 2 when $\ell \neq k$.

A. Case 1

When $\ell = k$, we have $\ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{\ell\ell}$ as the ℓ^{th} diagonal entry in $\ddot{\mathbf{S}}(C')$, and is defined as

$$\ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{\ell\ell} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell^2} & \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell \partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} \\ \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell \partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} & \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell^2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (33)$$

where the second-order derivatives are computed as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell^2} = 2\Re \left\{ (\mathbf{h}_r - \mathbf{A}_{C'} \mathbf{b}_{C'})^H \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell^2} \hat{\beta}'_\ell - |\hat{\beta}'_\ell|^2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} \right\}, \quad (34)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell^2} = 2\Re \left\{ (\mathbf{h}_r - \mathbf{A}_{C'} \mathbf{b}_{C'})^H \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell^2} \hat{\beta}'_\ell - |\hat{\beta}'_\ell|^2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} \right\}, \quad (35)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell \partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} &= \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell \partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} \\ &= 2\Re \left\{ (\mathbf{h}_r - \mathbf{A}_{C'} \mathbf{b}_{C'})^H \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell \partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} \hat{\beta}'_\ell - |\hat{\beta}'_\ell|^2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

B. Case 2

When $\ell \neq k$, we have $\ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{\ell k}$ as the (ℓ, k) -th off-diagonal entry in $\ddot{\mathbf{S}}(C')$, and is defined as

$$\ddot{\mathbf{S}}_{\ell k} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell \partial \hat{\tau}'_k} & \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell \partial \hat{\alpha}'_k} \\ \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_k \partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} & \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_k \partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (37)$$

where the second-order derivatives are computed as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_k \partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} = -2\Re \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_k, \hat{\alpha}'_k)}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_k} \hat{\beta}'_k \right)^H \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} \hat{\beta}'_\ell \right\},$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_k \partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} = -2\Re \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_k, \hat{\alpha}'_k)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_k} \hat{\beta}'_k \right)^H \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} \hat{\beta}'_\ell \right\}, \quad (39)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_k \partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} = -2\Re \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_k, \hat{\alpha}'_k)}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_k} \hat{\beta}'_k \right)^H \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_\ell} \hat{\beta}'_\ell \right\}, \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{S}(C')}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_k \partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} = -2\Re \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_k, \hat{\alpha}'_k)}{\partial \hat{\alpha}'_k} \hat{\beta}'_k \right)^H \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}(\hat{\tau}'_\ell, \hat{\alpha}'_\ell)}{\partial \hat{\tau}'_\ell} \hat{\beta}'_\ell \right\}, \quad (41)$$

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Thoma, T. Dallmann, S. Jovanoska, P. Knott, and A. Schmeink, "Joint Communication and Radar Sensing: An Overview," in *2021 15th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, pp. 1–5, IEEE, 3 2021.
- [2] J. Du, Y. Tang, X. Wei, J. Xiong, J. Zhu, H. Yin, C. Zhang, and H. Chen, "An Overview of Resource Allocation in Integrated Sensing and Communication," in *2023 IEEE/CIC International Conference on Communications in China (ICCC Workshops)*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 8 2023.
- [3] D. K. Pin Tan, J. He, Y. Li, A. Bayesteh, Y. Chen, P. Zhu, and W. Tong, "Integrated Sensing and Communication in 6G: Motivations, Use Cases, Requirements, Challenges and Future Directions," in *2021 1st IEEE International Online Symposium on Joint Communications & Sensing (JC&S)*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2 2021.
- [4] X. Cheng, D. Duan, S. Gao, and L. Yang, "Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) for Vehicular Communication Networks (VCN)," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, pp. 23441–23451, 12 2022.
- [5] S. N. H. Shah, D. Martín-Sacristán, C. Ravelo, C. Smeenk, C. Schneider, and J. Robert, "Radar-Enabled Resource Allocation in 5G-V2X Sidelink Communication," in *2023 IEEE 26th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*, pp. 1416–1421, IEEE, 9 2023.
- [6] V. Todisco, S. Bartoletti, C. Campolo, A. Molinaro, A. O. Berthet, and A. Bazzi, "Performance Analysis of Sidelink 5G-V2X Mode 2 Through an Open-Source Simulator," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 145648–145661, 2021.
- [7] M. L. Rahman, P.-f. Cui, J. A. Zhang, X. Huang, Y. J. Guo, and Z. Lu, "Joint Communication and Radar Sensing in 5G Mobile Network by Compressive Sensing," in *2019 19th International Symposium on Communications and Information Technologies (ISCIT)*, pp. 599–604, IEEE, 9 2019.
- [8] R. S. Thoma, C. Andrich, G. D. Galdo, M. Dobereiner, M. A. Hein, M. Kaske, G. Schafer, S. Schieler, C. Schneider, A. Schwind, and P. Wendland, "Cooperative Passive Coherent Location: A Promising 5G Service to Support Road Safety," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 57, pp. 86–92, 9 2019.
- [9] Z. Wan, Z. Gao, B. Shim, K. Yang, G. Mao, and M.-S. Alouini, "Compressive Sensing Based Channel Estimation for Millimeter-Wave Full-Dimensional MIMO With Lens-Array," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 69, pp. 2337–2342, 2 2020.
- [10] J. W. Choi, B. Shim, Y. Ding, B. Rao, and D. I. Kim, "Compressed Sensing for Wireless Communications: Useful Tips and Tricks," *IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials*, vol. 19, pp. 1527–1550, 7 2017.
- [11] M. A. Hadi, S. Alshebeili, K. Jamil, and F. E. El-Samie, "Compressive sensing applied to radar systems: an overview," *Signal, Image and Video Processing*, vol. 9, pp. 25–39, 12 2015.
- [12] J. H. Ender, "On compressive sensing applied to radar," *Signal Processing*, vol. 90, pp. 1402–1414, 5 2010.
- [13] C. R. Berger, B. Demissie, J. Heckenbach, P. Willett, and S. Zhou, "Signal Processing for Passive Radar Using OFDM Waveforms," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 4, pp. 226–238, 2 2010.

- [14] B. N. Bhaskar, G. Tang, and B. Recht, "Atomic Norm Denoising With Applications to Line Spectral Estimation," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 61, pp. 5987–5999, 12 2013.
- [15] Y. Chi, L. L. Scharf, A. Pezeshki, and A. R. Calderbank, "Sensitivity to Basis Mismatch in Compressed Sensing," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 59, pp. 2182–2195, 5 2011.
- [16] G. Hakobyan and B. Yang, "A Novel OFDM-MIMO Radar with Non-equidistant Subcarrier Interleaving and Compressed Sensing," in *2016 17th International Radar Symposium (IRS)*, pp. 1–5, IEEE, 5 2016.
- [17] G. Hakobyan and B. Yang, "A Novel OFDM-MIMO Radar with Non-equidistant Dynamic Subcarrier Interleaving," in *2016 European Radar Conference (EuRAD)*, pp. 45–48, IEEE, 2016.
- [18] B. Nuss, L. Sit, and T. Zwick, "A Novel Technique for Interference Mitigation in OFDM Radar using Compressed Sensing," in *2017 IEEE MTT-S International Conference on Microwaves for Intelligent Mobility (ICMIM)*, pp. 143–146, IEEE, 3 2017.
- [19] B. Kong, Y. Wang, H. Leung, X. Deng, H. Zhou, and F. Zhou, "Sparse Representation Based Range-Doppler Processing for Integrated OFDM Radar-Communication Networks," *International Journal of Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 2017, pp. 1–12, 2017.
- [20] C. Knill, B. Schweizer, S. Sparrer, F. Roos, R. F. H. Fischer, and C. Waldschmidt, "High Range and Doppler Resolution by Application of Compressed Sensing Using Low Baseband Bandwidth OFDM Radar," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 66, pp. 3535–3546, 7 2018.
- [21] C. Knill, F. Roos, B. Schweizer, D. Schindler, and C. Waldschmidt, "Random Multiplexing for an MIMO-OFDM Radar With Compressed Sensing-Based Reconstruction," *IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters*, vol. 29, pp. 300–302, 4 2019.
- [22] G. Tang, B. N. Bhaskar, P. Shah, and B. Recht, "Compressed Sensing Off the Grid," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 59, pp. 7465–7490, 11 2013.
- [23] S. Semper and F. Romer, "ADMM for ND Line Spectral Estimation Using Grid-free Compressive Sensing from Multiple Measurements with Applications to DOA Estimation," in *ICASSP 2019 - 2019 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pp. 4130–4134, IEEE, 5 2019.
- [24] B. Mamandipoor, D. Ramasamy, and U. Madhoo, "Newtonized Orthogonal Matching Pursuit: Frequency Estimation Over the Continuum," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 64, pp. 5066–5081, 10 2016.
- [25] M. Döbereiner, M. Käske, A. Schwind, C. Andrich, M. A. Hein, R. S. Thomä, and G. Del Galdo, "Joint High-Resolution Delay-Doppler Estimation for Bi-static Radar Measurements," in *2019 16th European Radar Conference (EuRAD)*, pp. 145–148, 2019.
- [26] A. U. Khan, S. N. H. Shah, C. Schneider, and J. Robert, "Target Detection in a Highway Scenario with Extended V2V Channel Model," in *2024 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 4 2024.
- [27] C. Sturm and W. Wiesbeck, "Waveform Design and Signal Processing Aspects for Fusion of Wireless Communications and Radar Sensing," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 99, pp. 1236–1259, 7 2011.
- [28] C. Ravelo, D. Martín-Sacristán, S. N. H. Shah, C. Smeenk, G. Del Galdo, and J. F. Monserrat, "Sensing Resources Reduction for Vehicle Detection with Integrated Sensing and Communications," in *2023 IEEE 97th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2023-Spring)*, pp. 1–5, IEEE, 6 2023.
- [29] M. F. Keskin, V. Koivunen, and H. Wymeersch, "Limited Feedforward Waveform Design for OFDM Dual-Functional Radar-Communications," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 69, pp. 2955–2970, 2021.
- [30] M. Hein, C. Bornkessel, W. Kotterman, C. Schneider, R. Sharma, F. Wolenschlager, R. Thoma, G. D. Galdo, and M. Landmann, "Emulation of virtual radio environments for realistic end-to-end testing for intelligent traffic systems," in *2015 IEEE MTT-S International Conference on Microwaves for Intelligent Mobility (ICMIM)*, pp. 1–4, IEEE, 4 2015.
- [31] A. Schwind, M. Döbereiner, C. Andrich, P. Wendland, G. Del Galdo, G. Schaefer, R. S. Thomä, and M. A. Hein, "Bi-static delay-Doppler reference for cooperative passive vehicle-to-X radar applications," *IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation*, vol. 14, pp. 1749–1757, 11 2020.
- [32] M. Piccardi, "Background subtraction techniques: a review," in *2004 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics (IEEE Cat. No.04CH37583)*, pp. 3099–3104, IEEE, 2004.

Syed Najaf Haider Shah received his B.Eng. degree in Electrical Engineering from the National University of Sciences and Technology (NUST), Islamabad, Pakistan in 2017 and his Masters degree in Electrical Engineering with majors in digital and wireless communication systems from Information Technology University (ITU), Lahore, Pakistan in 2020. Currently, he is pursuing his PhD from Technische Universität Ilmenau (TU Ilmenau), Germany. He is associated with the Electronic Measurements and Signal Processing group at TU Ilmenau. His research interests include waveform design for joint communication and radar sensing, optimal resource allocation algorithms design in vehicular networks, compressive sensing, and parameter estimation.

Dr.-Ing. S. Semper studied mathematics at Technische Universität Ilmenau, (TU Ilmenau), Ilmenau, Germany. He received the Master of Science degree in 2015. Since 2015, he has been a Research Assistant with the Electronic Measurements and Signal Processing Group, which is a joint research activity between the Fraunhofer Institute for Integrated Circuits IIS and TU Ilmenau, Ilmenau. In 2022 he finished his doctoral studies and received the doctoral degree with honors in electrical engineering. Since then, he has been a post doctoral student in the Electronic Measurements and Signal Processing Group. His research interest consist of compressive sensing, parameter estimation, optimization, numerical methods and algorithm design.

Aamir Ullah Khan received his BS degree in Electrical (Telecommunication) Engineering from COMSATS Institute of Information Technology (now known as COMSATS University (CUI)), Islamabad, Pakistan in 2015, and his Master's degree in Electronics and Communications Engineering from Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, Türkiye. He is currently pursuing his PhD degree at Technische Universität Ilmenau (TU Ilmenau), Ilmenau, Germany. He is associated with the Electronic Measurements and Signal Processing group at TU Ilmenau. His research interests include propagation modeling for Integrated Communication and Sensing (ICAS) enabled Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) systems, parameter estimation, and target detection in a clutter-rich environment.

Christian Schneider received his Diploma degree in electrical engineering from the Technische Universität Ilmenau, Germany in 2001. He is currently a group leader at the Electronic Measurements and Signal Processing department (EMS) at the TU Ilmenau as well as at Fraunhofer IIS. His research interests include multi-dimensional channel sounding, radio channel characterization and modeling, and its application to space-time signal processing and integrated sensing & communication (ISAC) questions. He received a best paper award at the European Wireless Conference in

2013 and the European Conference of Antennas and Propagation in 2017 and 2019.

Joerg Robert studied electrical engineering and information technology at TU Ilmenau and TU Braunschweig, Germany. From 2006 to 2012, he conducted research on the topic of digital television at the Institute of Communications Engineering at TU Braunschweig. Here he was actively involved in the development of DVB-T2, the second generation of digital terrestrial television. In 2013, he completed his PhD at TU Braunschweig on the topic of Terrestrial TV Broadcast using Multi-Antenna Systems. In 2012, he joined the LIKE chair at the Friedrich-Alexander-

Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany. One of his research topics focused on LPWAN (Low Power Wide Area Networks). Since 2021, he is full professor and head of the Group for Dependable Machine-to-Machine Communication at the Department of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology at Technische Universität Ilmenau, Germany. Joerg Robert is very active in international standardization. He currently is the secretary of the IEEE 802.15 standardization group, and the vice-chair of the IEEE 802.19.3 Task Group on wireless coexistence.